

The Comparative Study Criminal and Non-Criminal Women towards Men’s Attitude with Special Reference Dheradun Nagar

Divya Goswami¹ and Dr. Abhimanyu Kumar²

¹ *Researcher, Govt. P.G. College, Ranikhet, Almora,*

² *Supervisor Govt. P.G. College, Sitarganj, (U.S. Nagar)*

Received: 01.11.2024 | Accepted: 06.11.2024 | Published: 25.01.2025

*Corresponding Author: Divya Goswami¹ and Dr. Abhimanyu Kumar²

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14993929](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14993929)

Abstract	Original Research Article
<p>The present research paper in which the male respondents expressed their views on non-criminal and criminal women, on the basis of which the researcher put 10 questions in front of the male respondents and on that basis the views of respondent selected for Dehradun Nagar. This paper related to primary and secondary data. For example, women's thinking is limited to domestic matters; they take any decision keeping the family in mind, whereas men take decisions keeping the surrounding environment in mind. Women often go to their parents' home to express their displeasure, while men consume alcohol to express their displeasure? Most of the women often share all their things with men, along with this, women think of running the house by cutting down on household expenses, while men think about ensuring that the family members do not lack anything? It is based on this; apart from this the researcher also put other questions to the respondents whose details are given in the following table.</p> <p>Keywords: Criminal Women, Non-Criminal Women, Attitudes, Society, Thinking,</p>	

INTRODUCTION

Criminal women are those who have violated the legal rules, their criminal activities are against the morality and legal system of the society, many times difficult circumstances and external factors in their life lead to crime. The attitude of men towards women in the society has long been ingrained, especially when it comes to criminal women, the attitude of men in the society is influenced by patriarchal thinking and prejudices; Although this viewpoint has been changing over time, many important aspects were considered in this context in the decade of the 20th century. While men in traditional societies often view women as weak, sensitive, and tender, when a woman commits a crime it is seen as unusual and surprising, as men say women are not naturally capable of crime if they do

commit a crime, then there must be some external reason behind it, like mental imbalance, emotional stress or cruelty by some man, Social attitude towards women criminals In present times, with globalization, spread of education, the attitude of men towards women is changing, as their social expectations are also changing, as a result, men began to look at women's capabilities and responsibilities from a new perspective; they were no longer seen as mere victims or mentally deranged as before, but were held responsible for the crime¹.

Non-Criminal Women

India is a country where the land cannot be imagined without a woman, because here the land is worshipped as a mother and is considered as a deity, apart from this, it is also a matter of consideration

that to fight for the development of women, not only women but participation of men in women's organization is also essential in appropriate numbers because male members can raise various issues related to women in a better manner before other members of the society. For this, the role of men in women's organizations becomes even more important. In this context, many complaints are also received that women have falsely accused men in the matter of dowry, physical abuse, etc., for which an investigation is demanded. Therefore, by including men in these organizations, a logical balance will have to be established in the decisions taken in them, and then the decisions will not suffer from bias. Women act as the pillars of the society, their life is dedicated towards fulfilling their responsibilities towards their family, society and they contribute in various fields which help in the progress and development of the society. Their role is vital in important areas like education, health, social service Non-criminal women are playing a special role in the field of education, and they pay attention to the education of children as teachers, educators or mothers².

Review of Literature

Ingwer Borg, Dieter Hermann (2023) People's attitudes toward crimes and how they are related to gender, age, and personal values are studied here based on data from six representative surveys with altogether 14,591 respondents collected in four German cities between 1998 and 2020. The respondents rated fourteen legal offenses such as fare dodging, tax fraud, and car breaking on a "badness" scale. As predicted, women rate all offenses harsher than men and show more agreement in their ratings. As people grow older, their badness ratings rise monotonically in a decelerating way toward an upper asymptote. Exceptions are the youngest cohorts: They have relatively negative attitudes toward petty crimes (pot smoking, fare dodging), leading to initial dips in the growth curves. Personal values, in particular peoples' striving for conservation, predict people's badness ratings, most effectively for petty crimes, and independent of gender and age. In all age and gender sub-groups, crime-specific attitudes are positively inter-correlated, showing that there is a

common underlying attitude object. The structure of the badness items exhibits two dimensions, with highly similar configurations for all age and gender cohorts³.

Stephen A. Cernkovich and Peggy C. Giordano (1979) The historically dominant and generally accepted view is that males are much more likely than females to commit delinquent acts, and that when females deviate their misconduct is significantly less serious than that of males. This paper examines the recent contention that the delinquent behavior of males and females is more similar than assumed. Self-report questionnaires were administered in 1977 to a sample of 822 male and female adolescents selected from two urban high schools in a large Midwestern state. Following Hindelang (1971), we concentrate on the types of delinquent acts most frequently reported, as well as the extent of involvement in these acts. While males tend to commit most offenses more frequently than females, the pattern of delinquency is virtually identical for the two groups. This uniformity holds for race-sex subgroups, although there are more similarities in delinquency within racial groups than within sex groups⁴.

[Flood, Michael](#) & Pease, Bob (2006) this paper was prepared as part of the Violence against Women Community Attitudes Project. The project is one of a program of mental health promotion activities being undertaken by the Victorian Health Promotion Foundation to address violence against women. Violence against women is a prevalent problem with serious consequences for women's health. Intimate Partner Violence alone contributes 9% to the total disease burden in women aged 15-44 years and 60% of this is contributed by associated mental health problems. The Violence against Women Community Attitudes Project is being undertaken to gain a better understanding of community attitudes as a factor contributing to this problem⁵.

Research Objective

To study criminal and non-criminal women social status political status towards men attitudes
To Study criminal and non-criminal women family, educational status towards men attitudes

Research Methodology

In the present study, Dehradun city have been selected. The total number of these wards is 100, details of which have been obtained from Dehradun Municipal Corporation. Out of total 100 wards, The 06 wards were selected through

purposive sample. Thus, the total population of 06 wards is 42,605 Out of the total population of 423 respondents selected wards wise, 2 percent male respondents will be selected random sample. In the present study the researcher has used descriptive and exploratory research Method

Table 1:-Men's attitudes towards non-criminal and criminal women

Non-Criminal women				Criminal women		
S. No	Respondent Attitudes	Number	Percentage	Respondent Attitudes	Number	Percentage
1	Good	233	55	Good	255	60.28
2	Very good	106	25	Very good	64	15.13
3	General	63	15	General	15	3.55
4	Bed	21	5	Bed	89	21.04
Total		423	100	total	423	100

In the survey, the researcher tried to understand the attitude of the respondents towards non-criminal women and found that 233(55%) of the respondents had a positive attitude towards non-criminal women while 106(25%) of the respondents had a very good attitude towards non-criminal women Similarly, 63(15%) of the respondents had normal attitude while 21(5%) of the respondents had poor attitude towards the social status of non-criminal women. The researcher has tried to understand the attitude of men towards criminal women during the survey, in

which it was found that 255 (60.28%) of men had good attitude, 64 (15.28%) of respondents had positive attitude, while 15 (3.55%) percent of men had general attitude towards criminal women. And 89(21.04%) of the male criminals have bed thinking towards women. On the basis of above analysis, it can be said that the best thinking was of 255(60.28%) of the male non criminal's women, who have normal thinking towards women, i.e. their reaction was neither good nor bad.

Table.2:- Men's view on the current status of and non-criminal women

Noncriminal Women				Criminal women		
S. No.	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	%	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Goods	102	24	Goods	142	33.57
2	Very goods	228	54	Very goods	00	00
3	General	80	19	General	76	17.97
4	Beds	13	3	Beds	205	48.46
Total		423	100	Total	423	100

Table 2, the researcher tried to understand the respondents' view on the present status of non-criminal women during the survey in which it was found that 102 (24) percent of the respondents think that the present status of non-criminal women should

be good. While 228(54) per cent of the respondents had a very good attitude, 80(19) per cent of the respondents had a normal attitude while 13(3) per cent of the respondents had a poor attitude towards the current situation of non-criminal women. The

researcher tried to understand the views of men regarding the social status of criminal women during the survey and found that 142 (33.57) percent of male criminals have normal views about the social status of women criminals. While zero men have a good

attitude, 76(17.97) per cent of men have a bad attitude whereas 205(48.46) per cent of men do not give any response regarding the social status of criminal women.

Table.3:- Respondents' view on non-criminal and criminal educated women

Non-criminal Women				Criminal women		
S. No.	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	%	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Good	186	43.97	Good	00	00
2	Very good	118	27.90	Very good	47	11.11
3	General	85	20.09	General	121	28.61
4	Beds	34	8.04	Beds	255	60.28
Total		423	100		423	100

In table 3, the researcher tried to understand the perspective of the respondents during the survey on the education of non-criminal women and found that 186 (43.97) percent of the respondents had a positive opinion on the education of non-criminal women. While 118(27.90) per cent of the respondents have very good attitude, 85(20.09) per cent of the respondents have normal attitude while 34(8.04) per cent of the respondents have poor attitude towards educational status of non-criminal women. the

researcher tried to understand the views of men during the survey regarding the family status of criminal women and it was found that no man gave any response regarding the family status. While 255(60.28) per cent of men had no idea about the issue, 121(28.61) per cent of men had a normal attitude towards criminal women, 47(11.11) per cent of men had a bad attitude towards the family conditions of criminal women.

Table.4:- Respondents' view on criminal and non-criminal women being financially independent

Non-criminal Women				Criminal women		
S. No.	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	%	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	Percentage
	Goods	265	62.42	Goods	211	49.8
2	Very goods	73	17.25	Very goods	17	4.02
3	General	59	13.94	General	59	13.95
4	Beds	27	6.39	Beds	136	32.15
Total		423	100	Total	423	100

In table 4, the researcher tried to understand the opinion of the respondents during the survey on financial independence of non-criminal women and found that 265 (62.42)% of the respondents said yes on financial independence of non-criminal women. While 73(17.25) per cent of the respondents had a bad attitude, 59(13.94) per cent of the respondents had a mostly favorable attitude, 27(6.39) per cent of

the respondents had a poor attitude, i.e. they have no reaction on women becoming independent. During the survey, the researcher tried to understand the perspective of men on the impact of the crimes of female offenders on their families. It is clear from the survey that 211(49.88) percent of the men responded in the affirmative regarding the impact of the criminal woman on the family. Similarly 17(4.02)

percent of the men responded in the negative. Whereas 59(13.95) percent of the men responded n

the negative and 136(32.15) percent of the men did not know in this regard.

Table.5:- Men's attitudes towards family decisions of noncriminal and -criminal women

Non-criminal Women				Criminal women		
S. No.	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	%	Respondents attitude	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Goods	233	55.08	Goods	00	00
2	Very goods	106	2.06	Very goods	00	00
3	General	84	19.86	General	63	14.89
4	Beds	00	00	Beds	360	85.11
Total		423	100	Total	423	100

In table 5, the researcher tried to understand the respondents' views during the survey on self-determination of non-criminal women, in which it was found that 233 (55.08) percent of the respondents responded yes to While 106(25.06) percent of the respondents were not in favor of taking decisions. They said that it is alright for women to stay away from family decisions. 84(19.86) percent of the respondents were in favor of sometimes taking decisions while similarly zero respondents did not give any response. During the survey the researcher tried to know the viewpoint of male criminals regarding working women and found that 360(85.11) % of male criminals were not in favor of women working while 63(14.89)% of male criminals were in favor of working women .

Conclusion: - Studies have compared the attitudes of men and women towards crime, and the treatment of male and female by the criminal justice system.

These studies have found that women tend to have harsher attitudes towards crime than men, and that the treatment of male and female offenders by the criminal justice system in India. Society's attitude towards criminals is generally negative, with a belief that criminals should be punished for their actions. However, attitudes towards crime and criminals can change over time. The attitude of men towards women in the society has long been ingrained, especially when it comes to criminal women, the attitude of men in the society is influenced by patriarchal thinking and prejudices; Although this viewpoint has been changing over time, many important aspects were considered in this context in the decade of the 20th century. Whereas in traditional societies men often perceive women to be weak, sensitive, and tender, so when a woman commits a crime it is seen as unusual and surprising because men say women are not naturally capable of crime.

REFERENCES

1. Donohue, J. J. (1998). Understanding the time path of crime, *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 88, 1423-1451
2. Fagan, J., Zimring, F.E., & Kim, J. (1998). Declining homicide in New York City: A tale of two trends. *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 88, 1277-1323.
3. Pilgrim, David, Rogers, Anne (2005) "The Troubled Relationship Between Psychiatry and Sociology", *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*,: pp-229-241
4. Ingwer Borg, Dieter Hermann (2023) Attitudes toward crime and their relations to gender, age and personal values, *Current Research in behavioral sciences*, vol,4,pp-44-47

5. Stephen A. Cernkovich and Peggy C. Giordano (1979) A Comparative Analysis of Male and Female Delinquency, the Sociological Quarterly Vol. 20, No. 1
6. Flood, Michael & Pease, Bob (2006) *The Factors Influencing Community Attitudes in Relation to Violence Against Women: A Critical Review of the Literature*. Vic Health, Melbourne.
7. Kumar A. The Role Conflict among working Women: A Sociological Study (With reference to Ranikhet, Tehsil). J Criminology Forensic studies 2024, 6(1): 180076.
8. Bhandari M (2004) Women in Two Work Roles and the Quality of Human Life: Sociological Bulletin Vol 53 Issue 1 pp 94-104